

THE VOLATILE AND MINERALOGY MAPPING ORBITER (VMMO) LUNAR SCIENCE EXPLORATION MISSION – AN UPDATE AND CONOPS OUTLINE. R.V. Kruzelecky¹, I. Sinclair¹, A. Murzionak¹, Qi Yang Peng¹, D. Fermi¹, E. Cloutis², A. Cunje², D. Das², C. Tai Udovicic², D. Applin², H. Vannier², K. Ryden³, C. Underwood³, C.P. Bridges³, N. Baresi³, A. Lucca Fabris³, D. Morante⁴, B. Parreira⁵, C. António⁵, D. Esteves⁵, F. Formigão⁵, R. Prata⁵, A. Scott⁶, S. Hai Zheng⁶, J-F Hamel⁷, P. Woo⁷, M.-K. Langelier⁷, M. Gameiro⁸, J.M. Madariaga⁹, Z. Martins¹⁰, F. Rull Perez¹¹, G. L. Reyes¹¹, Y. Gao¹². ¹MPB Communications Inc. (MPBC) 147 Hymus Blvd., Pointe Claire, QC, Canada, roman.kruzelecky@mpbc.ca; ²University of Winnipeg, 515 Portage Ave. Winnipeg, MB, Canada, e.cloutis@uwinnipeg.ca; ³Surrey Space Centre, University of Surrey, Guildford, UK; ⁴Deimos Engineering and Systems SLU (DES), Calle Francia 9, Polígono Industrial La Nava III, Puertollano, Ciudad Real, Spain; ⁵Deimos Engenharia S.A. (DME), Av. Columbano Bordalo Pinheiro, No. 75, 9 A1 Lisboa, Portugal; ⁶Honeywell Limited, 155 Sheldon Drive, Cambridge, ON, Canada; ⁷NGC Aerospace Ltd., 2995, Boul. Industriel, Sherbrooke, QC, Canada; ⁸Critical Software, Parque Industrial de Taveiro, Lote 49, Coimbra, Portugal; ⁹University of the Basque Country, UPV/EHU, Bilbao, Spain; ¹⁰CQE, IMS and DEQ, Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal. ¹¹University of Valladolid, Palacio de Santa Cruz, 8, Valladolid, Spain; ¹²King's College London, Strand Building, Strand, London, UK.

Introduction: The south pole of the Moon remains an exploration target of high interest, and sustained manned presence on the lunar surface requires access to usable quantities of relevant in-situ resources such as water-ice, oxygen, and suitable building materials. While the evidence for lunar water ice stability and detection in permanently shadowed regions (PSRs) and cold traps at the south pole is compelling from numerous prior studies [1-3], major uncertainties exist in terms of its lateral extent and vertical distribution in the regolith, presence in terms of surficial concentrations/ratio, and associated lunar diurnal water-ice cycle.

The spatial resolution of the spectral observations of the prior and planned relevant lunar missions to detect signatures of water-ice are on the order of ~100 meters and greater, such as the ~280 x 280 m pixels of reported ice signatures derived from M3 data and consistent with other mission data [2]. Given that future lunar landers or rovers destined for PSRs will likely have limited mobility, there is a need to improve the spatial resolution and accuracy of maps of water ice in the lunar PSRs to the scale of 10s of metres.

The Lunar Volatile and Mineralogy Mapping Orbiter (VMMO) [4] lunar 16U Cubesat potential mission was initially developed by MPBC through the ESA SysNova LUCE competition. VMMO is currently in a Phase B1 study with ESA.

VMMO Design Overview: VMMO comprises a low-cost, highly capable 16U Cubesat, the Lunar Volatiles and Mineralogy Mapper (LVMM) science payload, the Surrey Compact LunAr Ionizing Radiation Environment (CLAIRE) radiation sensor suite, and the Deimos G3Star_Moon GNSS receiver demonstrator, to improve lunar data geolocation.

The VMMO spacecraft is designed to be transported to the Moon on a larger transport vehicle as part of a NASA CLPS mission or as part of an Ariane launch into a relevant weakly bound lunar injection orbit. It will be deployed using a spring-

loaded ring-type deployer. VMMO would be placed into polar orbit with the stability of a lunar frozen operational orbit characterized to give a perilune altitude of ~41 km over the south pole and an apolune altitude of ~200 km at the north pole.

VMMO Science Objectives: VMMO is designed to explore the presence and abundance of surficial water ice in PSRs and cold traps in the Moon's South Pole region, and map and quantify water-ice at high spatial resolution on the order of 10s of meters. Detection for water-ice will be done both during the lunar night (Active Mode), and lunar day (Passive Mode) to determine whether night-time frost deposition occurs and to study the lunar diurnal water-ice cycle via repeated geo-located surface measurements. VMMO will also extend daytime passive mode investigations into mineral and in-situ resource mapping across the lunar surface at and beyond the south pole. This will focus on ilmenite, spinels, hematite, and possible other volatile identification such as carbon dioxide ice. Additionally, VMMO will provide characterization of the cis-lunar radiation environment continually throughout its orbit and lifetime and determine its effects of total ionizing dose for applicability to health and instrumentation through its radiation sensor suite.

MPBC VMMO LVMM Science Payload: To meet these scientific objectives, the VMMO spacecraft will fly the LVMM multi-wave chemical Lidar payload which is being designed and developed by MPB Communications Inc. The payload itself weighs less than 8 kg and includes a 4 W 1064 nm to 532 nm SHG, a 20 W PM fiber-laser at 1064 nm, a 4W fiber laser at 1560 nm, a broadband multispectral receiver with 80 mm O.D. primary aperture operating near 300, 532, 690, 850, 1064, 1350, 1560 and 1650 nm using one PCO-Panda UV-enhanced CMOS imager and two 640CSX SWIR InGaAs imagers, one dedicated to 1064 nm and the other to 1350, 1560 and 1650 nm.

The LVMM spectral bands and their primary applicability to the science goals via spectral analyses are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of LVMM Bands and Uses

Wavelength (nm)	Mode: Active/Passive	Primary Purpose/Context
300	P	Ilmenite detection band (< 600 nm) (absorption band around 300 nm, determine ratio with VIS 532 nm band [5,7])
532	A, P	Band for ratios used in determining presence, form, abundance of water ice, ilmenite [5,6,7]
690	P	Spinel detection band - absp. ~660 nm; constrain optical maturity of materials via slope [7]
850	P	Hematite detection band [5,7]
1064	A, P	Band for ratio used in determining presence, form, abundance of ices. [6,7] Lunar mare absorption bands in region due to the mafic silicates (pyroxene and olivine)
1350	P	Plagioclase detection band [6,7]
1560	A, P	Water band for ratio used in determining presence, form, and abundance. Key band for characterizing strong water ice absorption and weaker CO ₂ ice absorption. [6,8]
1650	P	Characterize shape and ratio of mafic silicate absorption in 1000 nm region; correlates with optical maturity and mafic silicate composition and abundance [6,7]

Active Mode- Goals and ConOps: The 532, 1064, and 1560 nm active bands are to be used in the primary goal of water-ice detection during lunar night and in targeting PSRs [6]. This will provide a unique opportunity to characterize water-ice at target locations of interest without reliance on scattered sunlight. A SNR of 100:1 is achievable with altitudes of at least 80 km for all 3 bands, and greater spatial resolution is expected over the south pole with lower integration times along track for the active beams, giving footprints of 10x50 m. Reflectance ratios between the bands can be used with absolute reflectance values to determine the presence and concentration of potential water ice signals down to concentrations of 2wt% and lower [6].

Passive Mode- Goals and ConOps: In addition to their active modes, the 3 main bands can also operate in passive mode along with the bands listed in Table 1. A UV-VIS-NIR range is covered for daytime observations for the goals of mapping various resources, with each band able to lend to a particular material detection for spectral ratios and the full range of bands allowing for more comprehensive spectral shape and slope characterization (including reddening/optical maturity) with a spatial resolution on the order of 24 m GSD near perilune altitudes.

Hybrid Mode Option: The active mode lasers may also be used intermittently during lunar day

when targeting PSRs and presents the option of a hybrid mode observation set; both the active mode laser light and passive mode back-reflected sunlight sources would be measured, summed together, and imaged onto the detector arrays to provide high spatial resolution measurements at about 10 m for the 3 key bands at low perilune altitudes of 40 – 50 km.

LVMM Targets of Interest and Coverage: The primary targets of interest for LVMM's volatile search include the south pole craters suggested to host the most surficial water ice, such as Faustini, Cabeus, Haworth, and Shoemaker [3], along with the reported collection of M3 ice-detection targets [2]. Other targets include potential ilmenite sources in the equatorial region, previous mission sites for calibration, and future mission sites for further characterization. Initial coverage analyses provide near 100% coverage of targets in passive mode, with active mode providing better coverage at higher latitudes, and improved with active steering capabilities.

Surrey CLAIRE Radiation Sensor Suite:

CLAIRE is composed of three main detector sub systems to record and characterize the energetic proton and heavy ion particle fluxes and LET spectra due to galactic-cosmic rays and any solar energetic particle events that occur during the mission, and can provide insight via derived total ionizing dose on potential harm to electronic and human health caused by the radiation environment. It will operate continuously over the mission duration to record spatial variations over the lunar orbit and temporal variations caused by changes in solar activity.

Conclusions: The data collected by LVMM in its various modes can address key unknowns about the distribution of relevant lunar volatiles and resources to provide guidance for potential future landed mission operations to reduce their risks.

The mission will also provide data on the cis-lunar radiation environment using the CLAIRE sensor suite to assist lunar orbit and surface studies and future potential manned mission planning.

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